

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>**Research Article****A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH ON THE MEDICAL
PROFESSION INSTRUCTOR'S PEDAGOGICAL AND
ANDRAGOGICAL ATTITUDE AND APTITUDE AT WAH
MEDICAL COLLEGE****¹Dr. Hafiz Muhammad Ali, ²Dr. Aamir Hayat, ³Dr. Muhammad Sohaib**¹Senior Medical Officer, PKLI-HPTC, Narowal²Medical Officer, BHU Chak No.218/TDA, Layyah³Medical Officer, BHU Mianwala Pindigheb Attock**Abstract:**

Introduction: Teachers who show positive attitudes towards their professions also express dedication towards their nation, which emphasizes their strength of responsibility. (1) A detailed assessment of teachers' attitudes towards teaching is essential for monitoring the progress and efficacy of classroom management in creating a setting conducive to the learning process of the students and professional reward of the teachers. Once these essential refinements have been made, an education system is able to flourish.

Objective: To assess teacher's attitude towards teaching by comparing the reported attitudes on basis of questionnaires.

Study design: cross sectional study design.

Place and duration: The research was conducted at WAH medical college and National Defense University and the duration of study was 6 months.

Methodology: Research was conducted on teachers. Closed ended questionnaires were used to assess teacher's attitude. Data collected was analyzed on SPSS version 19. Proportions were calculated and data then presented in table, pic and bar charts.

Results: 48% of participants were made and 51.5% were assistant or associate professors and 35.2% were professors. 64.8% of self-assessment and 62.7% of peers said that they adopted teaching as their first choice for career. A chi-square was applied for the analysis, and significant difference was found in teacher's attitude assessed by themselves and their peers.

Conclusion: Self and peer assessments of teachers' attitude towards the teaching profession were found to be meaningful. On the basis of questionnaire responses, both selfassessments and peer-assessments reported that the attitude of teachers towards teaching is significantly positive. There is no discrimination on the basis of gender, designation, or teaching experience.

Keywords: Evaluation, Teachers, Attitudes, Profession, WAH medical college, national defense university.

Corresponding Author:**Dr. Hafiz Muhammad Ali,**

Senior Medical Officer,

PKLI-HPTC, Narowal

QR code

Please cite this article in press Hafiz Muhammad Ali et al., *A Cross-Sectional Research on the Medical Profession Instructor's Pedagogical and Andragogical Attitude and Aptitude at Wah Medical College*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(06).

INTRODUCTION:

Teachers who show positive attitudes towards their professions also express dedication towards their nation, which emphasizes their strength of responsibility. (1) A detailed assessment of teachers' attitudes towards teaching is essential for monitoring the progress and efficacy of classroom management in creating a setting conducive to the learning process of the students and professional reward of the teachers. Once these essential refinements have been made, an education system is able to flourish. (2) . There are few records, if any, of this study being performed anywhere in Pakistan. Therefore, it is of the utmost importance for us to conduct this assessment of teachers' attitudes towards teaching for feedback and possible improvement of teaching in Pakistan. For this purpose, two institutions have been selected: Wah Medical College, Wah Cantt, and National Defense University, Islamabad. Both are highly organized institutions affiliated with the armed services, and award advanced educational degrees in medicine and social sciences, respectively. By examining the attitudes of teachers towards their profession in these two institutions, we will be able to assess how teachers acknowledge students' learning needs, as well as make effective use of their own professional sensibilities. This study will allow us to determine the responses of teachers to different teaching and learning environments. We will be able to create a profile of how teachers develop their attitudes towards their profession as well as their students, which opens up the possibilities of improving the delivery of education to students and enhancing the professional skills of teachers in both Wah Medical College and National Defense University. These improvements can, in turn, be promoted and implemented in the education system of Pakistan to provide teachers and students with the best possible professional and educational environment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A questionnaire with a five-point rating scale was personally administered by the researchers to the sample faculties. Analysis of the results showed that the majority of teachers who were surveyed felt proud of their status as teachers. They strived to improve their knowledge of respective subjects and teaching skills by participating in professional developmental activities and preparing their lectures daily. Results of the assessment also indicated that the majority of faculty members considered "punctuality," "honesty," and "hardworking" to be the three most important qualities of a teacher's behavior. According to the responses, most teachers felt they listened to students with patience and

tolerance and guided them in their spare time, while making sure to award marks in exams without discrimination. A third study performed in Tamil Nadu, India (6), utilized two sets of questionnaires: one for assessing high school teachers' attitudes towards their professions and one for assessing high school teachers' attitudes towards their respective administrations. The teachers belonged to self-financing and governmentaided high schools in both rural and urban areas. The results obtained showed that both male and female high school teachers had positive attitudes towards both their profession and administrations, especially those who are above 30 years of age.

Study Design:

Cross sectional study

Study Setting:

- Wah Medical College (WMC)
- National Defense University (NDU)

Duration of Study:

6 Months

Sample Size:

80% of the total target population

Sampling Technique:

Convenient sampling

Sampling Tool:

Closed-ended questionnaire

Data Collection Procedure:

Data will be collected from the teachers of WMC and NDU by administering the questionnaires to the respective faculties twice. Teachers from each faculty will fill in one questionnaire for themselves and one for their peers. The questions will be asked in English.

Data Analysis Procedure:

Data will be entered into SPSS Version 19. Mean, median, and mode will be calculated for all the variables in the questionnaire. The mean attitude score of each teacher will also be calculated, and they will be categorized into five categories, as stated in the Operational Definition. Proportions will be calculated, and the data will be presented in tables, pie charts, and bar charts.

Test of significance: a Chi-square test will be applied to test the difference/association between:

- Self and peer-reported responses on questions asked
 - Attitude score and gender
 - Attitude score and designation
 - Attitude score and teaching experience
 - Attitude score and teaching institute
- The level of significance (α) will be taken at 0.05.

RESULTS:

This study was done to study the self- and peer-reported attitude of teachers teaching in a professional college or university towards teaching. A new questionnaire was designed by 4th year students, which included questions on demographic variables along with their designation, teaching experience, and whether or not teaching was their first career choice. Attitude was assessed on the basis of 32 Likert scale questions, which were constructed in the light of the literature review and input from the supervisor.

Ninety-one teachers returned the questionnaire on self assessment of their attitudes. The same questionnaire was distributed again for a peer assessment in the same departments, out of which 59 were returned, as shown in Table 1.

Fifty-eight percent of participants were from Wah Medical College, and the remaining 41.8% were from National Defense University, as shown in Table 2.

Forty eight percent of participants involved in this research were males, and 51.6% were females, as shown in Table 3.

Forty one percent participants had 0-5 years of teaching experience; 30% had between 6 to 10 years of teaching experience; and the remaining 32% had more than 10 years of teaching experience. The details regarding these results are given in Table 4.

Teachers who had a postgraduate degree comprised 65.9% of the sample, and the remaining 34.1% were graduates, as shown in Table 5.

In this study, 46.2% of the participants were either lecturers or senior lecturers; 15.4% were either assistant professors or associate professors; and 35.2% were professors. The details are shown in Table 6.

When teachers were asked whether or not teaching was their first choice to adopt as a career, 64.8% said "yes" on self assessment, and an almost equal percentage (62.7%) of peers also said "yes." Results are displayed in Table 7.

A majority of teachers (88% on self and 85% on peer assessment) either agreed or strongly agreed that teaching is an ennobling profession, whereas 9.9% and 13.6% remained neutral on self and peer assessment, respectively. The rest disagreed with the statement, as presented in Figure 1.

While self-reporting on whether or not teachers adopted this profession to enhance their earning capabilities, 45% either strongly agreed or agreed; 26% remained neutral; and 27.5% disagreed or strongly disagreed with this statement. Their peers reported that 37% adopted teaching for increased earning, while 44% remained neutral, and 18.7% disagreed/strongly disagreed with this statement, as shown in Figure 2.

Teachers who liked to participate in co-curricular activities represented 64.9% of the sample; 23.9% had a neutral opinion; and the rest (12.9%) were against this notion.

Self- and peer-reported responses are presented in Figure 3.

The majority of participants (96.1%) and their peers (93.2%) were of the opinion that it is important for them to prepare their lectures daily before going to class; the rest were either neutral or disagreed with this notion. Results are displayed in Figure 4.

In this study, 78% of the participants strongly agreed or agreed that they feel comfortable delivering lectures on multimedia; 14.3% were neutral; and only 6.6% felt uncomfortable with this activity. Peers had almost similar opinions about their colleagues, as shown in Figure 5.

In both institutes, 91.2% of participants agreed that they maintain a friendly relationship with their students; 3% were neutral; and 5% disagreed. Among their peers, 78% agreed/strongly agreed; 16.9% remained neutral; and 5.1% disagreed/strongly disagreed, as shown in Figure 6.

Eighty-five percent of all the participants and 84.8% of their peers made effective eye contact with their students; 7.7% were unable to make effective eye contact with students; and 6.6% were neutral, as shown in Figure 7.

According to the results, 85.5% of the teachers and 67.8% of their peers agreed that they enjoy participating in different educational activities offered by educational organizations. Eleven percent remained neutral about themselves, whereas 18.6% of peers remained neutral about their colleagues. Only a few (3.3%) said they do not enjoy such activities, whereas their colleagues reported a frequency of 13.6%, as shown in Figure 8.

Eighty-six percent of the participants and 85% of their colleagues indicated that they were devoted

towards students, while the rest were either neutral (11% in self assessment and 11.9% in peer assessment) or against this claim (2.2% in self assessment and 1.7% in peer assessment), as shown in Figure 9.

Self-reported regularity and punctuality was 85%, but peers testified to only 79.6% being regular and punctual, while 5.5% teachers admitted that they were not very regular and punctual. A little more than 15% of colleagues remained neutral about their co-workers. Detailed results are displayed in Figure 10.

Analysis shows that 69.3% of participants were in favor of a formative assessment; 26.4% had a neutral opinion; and only 4.4% opposed this, as shown in Figure 11.

A significant number of participants (82.5%) agreed to positively accepting difference of opinion of their students, while the peer assessment expressed this quality in 79.7% of teachers. Almost 11% were neutral about themselves, and 15.3% of peers were neutral about their colleagues. Only a few (6.6%) admitted to not accepting their students' difference of opinion, as shown in Figure 12.

A notable percentage (88.1%) of the participants and their peers affirmed that they consider it to be their duty to listen and guide their students in their free time, while 10% and 2% harbored neutral and contrary opinions, respectively. Results are displayed in Figure 13.

About 37% of teachers (in both self and peer assessments), either agreed or strongly agreed that students show little respect for their teachers nowadays, while 22% and 13.6% stayed neutral, and 11% and 49.2% were against this notion in self and peer assessments, respectively, as shown in Figure 14.

A major proportion of the participants (89%) agreed that interactive learning is beneficial for students, while 5.5% of teachers disagreed with the statement, as shown in Figure 15.

A greater portion of the participants (86.9%) admitted to feeling responsible for grooming a student's personality as a whole in addition to imparting knowledge, whereas their peers implied this as being true for 79.7% of their co-workers. Three percent opposed this notion, while 9.9% and 16.9% remained impartial for themselves and their peers, as shown in Figure 16.

Fifty-six percent of teachers agreed with the statement that intelligent students should be isolated and taught separately, whereas 22% disagreed, and 21.4% were impartial, as shown in Figure 17.

A notable percentage (92%) agreed that all staff members should work together to make strategies beneficial for students' learning, while the remaining 8% had other opinions, as shown in Figure 18. Thirty-eight percent and 34% were in agreement and disagreement, respectively, that negative incentives have positive effects on students' academic performance; 28% did not favor either extreme, as shown in Figure 19.

Participants whose performance was affected by financial incentives (23% and 21%) were neutral or disagreed with the statement, respectively, as shown in Figure 20.

Almost an equal number of the participants (41% and 40%) agreed and disagreed, respectively, that their health problems do not affect their teaching abilities, while 19% showed a neutral response, as shown in Figure 21.

Most of the participants (64%) admitted that they do not let their personal problems diminish their professional performance; 26% were neutral; and a relatively small percentage (9%) disagreed with this idea, as shown in Figure 22.

A noteworthy 91% of the participants suggested that a friendly departmental environment encourages them to provide effective educational output as teacher, and the 9% had other perspectives, as shown in Figure 23.

The participants who admitted authoritative leadership is a hindrance in delivering maximum educational output were surveyed to be 73%; 22% were neutral; and just 5% said otherwise, as shown in Figure 24.

A significant percentage (74%) of participants agreed that non-availability of basic necessities negatively influences their attitude as a teacher, while 15% opposed this statement, and 11% remained neutral, as shown in Figure 25.

More than half (66.7%) of the participants either agreed or strongly agreed that hostile administrative behavior creates personal distress, which results in an abysmal attitude towards students. Fourteen percent did not agree with the statement, and the remaining 19.3% were neutral, as shown in Figure 26.

Fifty-eight percent of the participants in the study agreed that a poor performance/feedback by students decreased their motivational approach towards teaching; 25% shared neutral thoughts; and the rest (18%) were in disagreement with this statement, as shown in Figure 27.

A considerable percentage (86%) liked teaching and was happy when with students; just 2.7% were of the opposite opinion; and 11.3% chose to remain neutral, as shown in Figure 28.

In both institutes, 43.6% of participants were satisfied with the administration of their institution, while 26.8% remained neutral, and 29.5% implied that they were not satisfied with their administrations, as shown in Figure 29.

An appreciable percent (82%) of the participants indicated that they are keen to consult books or internet sources related to their subject; 10% were neutral; and 8% indicated that they do not perform the aforementioned activity, as shown in Figure 30.

Almost 81% agreed that they feel a sense of achievement towards their profession; 15% were neutral; and just 4% disagreed with this statement, as shown in Figure 31.

In the analysis, 54% either agreed or strongly agreed that they are satisfied with the basic facilities provided by their institution, as shown in Figure 32.

The Chi-square test was applied to find out the association of teachers' attitude score with their designation; teaching experience; teaching as their first choice; gender; and the teaching institute they belonged to. Self-reported attitude scores were better for WMC employees and female teachers. All other associations were negative. The results are shown in Table 8. However, a significant difference was found in teachers' attitudes assessed by themselves and by their peers, with $\chi^2 = 15.073$, $df = 3$ and $p = 0.002$. These results are displayed in Table 8, as well.

Table 1: Frequency of Participants who Provided Self or Peer Assessment

Type of Assessment	Frequency	Percent
Self only	91	60.7
Self & Peer	59	39.3
Total	150	100.0

Table 2: Frequency Distribution Table showing Institutions of the Study Participants

Institute	Frequency	Relative frequency
Wah Medical College	53	58.2
National Defense University	38	41.8
Total	91	100

Table 3: Gender-wise Frequency of Participants who Provided either Self or Both Assessments

Gender	Frequency (%) providing Self assessment	Frequency (%) providing Self & peer assessments
Male	44 (48.4)	24 (40.7)
Female	47 (51.6)	35 (59.3)
Total	91 (100)	59 (100)

Table 4: Frequency Distribution Table showing Teaching Experience of the Study Participants

Experience	Frequency	Percent
0-5 years	36	39.6
6-10 years	27	29.7
11-15 years	20	22.0
16-20 years	2	2.2
>20 years	6	6.5
Total	91	100

Table 5: Frequency Distribution Table showing Qualification of the Study Participants

Qualification	Frequency	Percent
Graduate	31	34.1
Post graduate	60	65.9
Total	91	100

Table 6: Frequency Distribution Table showing Designations of the Study Participants

Designation	Frequency	Percent
Lecturer	38	41.8
Senior lecturer	4	4.4
Assistant professor	14	15.4
Associate professor	3	3.3
Professor	32	35.2
Total	91	100

Table 7: Participants' Response for "Was teaching your first career choice?"

Choice	Response on Self assessment f(%)	Response on peer assessment f(%)
Yes	59 (64)	37 (62.7)
No	32 (35.1)	22 (37.2)
Total	91	59

Figure 1: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Teaching is an Ennobling Profession

Figure 2: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Teaching Profession was Chosen to Enhance Earning Capabilities

Figure 3: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Participation in Cocurricular Activities is Preferred

Figure 4: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Lectures are Prepared Daily

on

Figure 5: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Comfortable with Delivering Lectures Multimedia

Figure 6: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not a Friendly Relationship is maintained with Students

Figure 7: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Effective Eye Contact with Students is Made

Figure 8: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether Participation in Various Educational Activities is Preferred

Figure 9: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Devoted towards Students

Figure 10: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Regular and Punctual

Figure 11: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not in Favor of Formative Assessment

Figure 12: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Accepting of Difference of Opinion of Students

Figure 13: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Listening to and Guiding Students is Routinely Practiced

Figure 14: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Students Show Little Respect for their Teachers Nowadays

Figure 15: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Interactive Learning is Beneficial for Students

Figure 16: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Responsible for Grooming a Student's Personality

Figure 17: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Intelligent Students should be Isolated and Taught Separately

Figure 18: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not All Staff Members should Work Together to make Strategies Beneficial for Students' Learning

Figure 19: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Negative Incentives have a Positive Impact on Students' Academic Performance

Figure 20: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Financial Incentives Affect Own Performance

Figure 21: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Health Problems Affect Own Teaching Abilities

Figure 22: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Personal Problems Affect Own Professional Performance

Figure 23: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not a Friendly Departmental Environment Encourages Provision of Effective Educational Output as a Teacher

Figure 24: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Authoritative Leadership is a Hindrance in Delivering Maximum Output as a Teacher

Figure 25: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Non-Availability of Basic Necessities Negatively Influences Attitude as a Teacher

Figure 26: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Hostile Administrative Behavior Creates Personal Distress

Figure 27: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Poor Performance by Students Decreases Motivational Approach towards Teaching

Figure 28: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Satisfied with Profession

Figure 29: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Satisfied with Administration

Figure 30: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Keen on Consulting Books and Internet Sourced Related to Subject

Figure 31: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Sense of Achievement towards Profession is Felt

-Figure 32: Self- and Peer-Reported Response on Whether or Not Satisfied with Basic Facilities of Own Institution

Table 8: Chi-Square Test Results: differences in the self- and peer-reported teachers' attitudes score and their designations; teaching experience; teaching as the first choice of profession; gender; and teaching institute.

Variable	Self assessment		Peer assessment	
	Chi-square value	P value	Chi-square value	P value
Gender	8.09	0.04	4.09	0.11
Designation	24.3	0.01	20.8	0.05
Teaching Experience	10.51	0.13	5.67	0.43
Teaching Institute	14.6	0.002	3.37	0.33
Teaching as first choice	3.81	0.23	8.64	0.02

Grouping variable	Self reported score	Peer reported score
Institute		
WMC	95	89
NDU	86	94
Gender		
Male	88	94
Female	94	90
Designation		
Lecturer/sr. lecturer	92	91
AP & above	90	92
Experience		
<15 years	91	92
>15 years	101	87
Teaching first choice		
Yes	90	94
No	94	87

Table 9: Difference between Self and Peer assessment: chi-square test

	Self or Peer assessments		Total
	Self	Peer	
Total score 70-85	13	12	25
86-100	64	34	98
101-115	14	13	27
Total	91	59	150

Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymp. (2sided)	Sig.
Pearson Chi-Square	2.550 ^a	2	.279	
Likelihood Ratio	2.530	150	.282	
N of Valid Cases				

a. 0 cells (.0%) have expected count less than 5. The minimum expected count is 9.83.

Table 10: Mean and median attitude score of teachers on self and peer assessment.

Type of assessment	Self	Peer
No of respondents	91	59
Mean attitude score	91.6	94.00
Median attitude score	92.06	90.00

Fig 33: Self & peer reported attitude scores distributed in categories.

DISCUSSION:

This research has been conducted to assess the attitude of teachers towards teaching profession. The purpose of the study was to assess the difference of attitude when the given questionnaires were filled by the teachers themselves (self) and also for other teachers (peer). For this study, the questionnaires were filled by the teachers of WMC and NDU. This research was conducted at WMC from January 1st to 30th August. This research was supervised by Dr. Musarrat Ramzan and assisted by Dr. Ambreen.

Our results are similar to the results of the reference researches including Ahmadabad

India (1), Hyderabad city (5), Tamil Nadu India (6), Aligarh India (7), St. Xavier's college in Ranchi Jharkhand India (8), Dokuz Eylul university Turkey (3), Inonu university (10), Bucharest center of educational resources Romania (11), University of Chicago press (4). According to these results, teachers exhibit positive attitude toward their profession and feel proud about their profession. Punctuality, honesty and hardworking are the most important qualities of a teacher's behavior. Teachers felt that their choice is best and displayed high levels of professional enthusiasm towards their profession. A positive correlation was observed between the cognitive and affective components.

Teachers were able to maintain positive class room environment and discipline.

Our research results were different from the some reference researches such as West Bengal India (9) research in which 8.5% show positive attitude where as 25% show negative attitude and Sultan Qaboos University Oman (2) which show some sort of negative attitude.

Questionnaires were distributed for self and peer assessment. Both of the questionnaires have the similar response between the peer and self and there was no significant difference. Few questions show dissimilarity and a significant difference between self and peer assessment like ,preparing the lectures daily before going to class, friendly relationship with students, enjoy participating in different educational activities,favour of formative assessment, little respect shown by the students for their teachers, participation of staff members beneficial for students learning, authoritative leadership causing hindrance in delivering the maximum output ,poor performance/feedback by students and satisfaction achieved by basic facilities provided by the institution.Therefore,positive efforts should be done in the above fields to improve the teacher's performance.

CONCLUSION:

Self and peer assessments of teachers' attitude towards the teaching profession were found to be meaningful. On the basis of questionnaire responses, both selfassessments and peer-assessments reported that the attitude of teachers towards teaching is significantly positive. There is no discrimination on the basis of gender, designation, or teaching experience. When questions were asked about whether the teaching was their first choice to adopt as carrier or not? 64.8% said yes on self assessment, and 62.7% were neutral, 11% and 49.2% were against this statement in self and peer assessment. Respectively, 89% approved that interactive learning is beneficial for the students while 5.5% disagree about this. 86.9% were confirmation of the fact that they feel responsible for grooming the students personality as a whole while peer claims to be true for 79.7% of their coworker. 56% and 22% agreed and disagreed to isolate the intelligent students. 92% agreed to work together to device the policies beneficial for students and 38% were agreed that negative reinforcement is good for students. 91% claim that there should be friendly learning environment. Chi-square was applied and found that self reported is better.

REFERENCES:

1. Issan S, Al-Nabhani H, Kazem A, Al-Ani W. Omani Teachers' Attitude towards Teaching as a profession. ResearchGate 2011 july . Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/270703648_Omani_Teachers'_Attitude_s_towards_the_Teaching_Profession_Omani_Teachers'_Attitudes_towards_Teaching_as_a_Profession
2. Oruc N. The perception of teaching as a profession by Turkish Trainee Teachers: Attitudes towards being a teacher. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science. 2011;1(4):83-7. Available at: http://www.ijhssnet.com/journals/Vol._1_No._4;_April_2011/11.pdf
3. Rimm-Kaufman SE, Sawyer BE. Primary-grade teachers' self-efficacy beliefs, attitudes toward teaching, and discipline and teaching practice priorities in relation to the "responsive classroom" approach. The Elementary School Journal. 2004 Mar 1:321-41. Available at: https://www.jstor.org/stable/3202945?seq=1#page_scan_tab_contents
4. Mehdipour Y, Balaramulu D. Teacher's Attitude toward Their Work and Performance in Hyderabad Universities. IJIRS. 2013 May;2(5):311-323. Available at: http://www.ijirs.com/vol2_issue-5/25.pdf
5. C D. Attitude of teachers towards Their Profession and Administration. 2014 Aug;5(4):69-74. Available at: <http://www.the-criterion.com/V5/n4/DivyaC.pdf>
6. Trivedi RP. A study of attitude of teachers towards teaching profession teaching at different level. International Multidisciplinary e-Journal. 2012;1(5):24-30. Available at: <http://www.shreeprakashan.com/Documents/20126154238677.5.Rohini%20P.Tri%20ved.pdf>
7. Andronache D, Bocos, M, Bocos, V, Macri C. Attitude towards teaching profession. 2014 Aug 14;142(2014):628-632. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/275543882_Attitude_Towards_Teaching_Profession_&http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877042814046059.
8. Bhargava A, Pathy MK. Attitude of Student Teachers towards Teaching Profession. Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education. 2014 Jul;15(3):27-36. Available at: <http://dergipark.ulakbim.gov.tr/tojde/article/view/5000102127/5000095226>
9. Parvez M, Shakir M. Attitudes of prospective teachers towards teaching profession. Journal of

Education and Practice. 2013;4(10):172-178. Available at: [http://pakacademicsearch.com/pdf-files/edu/413/172-178%20Vol%204,%20No%2010%20\(2013\).pdf](http://pakacademicsearch.com/pdf-files/edu/413/172-178%20Vol%204,%20No%2010%20(2013).pdf)

10. Üstüner M, Demirtas H, Cömert M. The attitudes of prospective teachers towards the profession of

teaching (The case of Inonu University, Faculty of Education). *EgitimveBilim*. 2009 Jan 1;34(151):140. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/279900735_The_attitudes_of_prospectve_teachers_towards_the_profession_of_teaching_the_case_of_inonu_university_faculty_of_education